

Data Management Plan for the Project "Contextualization of Traditional Clothing: Reassessing the Connection Between Riga and Latgale"

Version 1

Description

This is the Data management plan for the research project Contextualization of Traditional Clothing: Reassessing the Connection Between Riga and Latgale. This project provides a new understanding of traditional clothing and its context as a valuable source for interdisciplinary research of social history of poorly documented communities. It is based on a systematic critical analysis of historiography, archival, and object-based studies. It is an interdisciplinary study that integrates the approaches and methodology of dress history, ethnology, microhistory, and historical anthropology to contextualize traditional clothing. The project studies the characteristics and context of traditional clothing in Riga worn until the 1840s, and how its influence reached Latgale, the farthest rural region of Latvia. The project investigates significant connections between the traditional dress of Latgalian peasants and the common Rigans: Latvian, German, Russian, and Jewish working people.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Internal and External
Consolidation of the University

of Latvia

Researchers

Ieva Pigozne (0000-0003-1726-0928)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data Management Plan for the Project "Contextualization of Traditional Clothing: Reassessing the Connection Between Riga and Latgale"](#)

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Organizations:

[University of Latvia](#)

Contact: [Pigozne Ieva \(ieva.pigozne@lu.lv\)](mailto:ieva.pigozne@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: [Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia](#)

Project: [Contextualization of Traditional Clothing: Reassessing the Connection Between Riga and Latgale](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2025-02-28](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Visual and written sources on traditional clothing in Riga during the 18th and 19th centuries

This dataset contains metadata, descriptions, and texts of visual and written sources on traditional clothing in Riga during the 18th and 19th centuries. The original sources are stored at the archives and collections of various memory institutions. This dataset contains data on what information they can provide for dress historians and social history researchers.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Textual data
- Other

Translations of historical textual primary sources

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

I am creating a new dataset for this project, which will be shared on Zenodo. During my research, I will use data from my previous work to compare with the newly obtained data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Latvian and international dress historians and social history researchers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Data Package

Metadata will contain information on the sources from which data are obtained: their author, collection, content, date of creation, form of the source etc.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

No specific software tools or methods are needed to access the data.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-08-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

Data will be made reusable by third parties after the end of the project.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ieva Pigozne (0000-0003-1726-0928)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The primary sources stored in museums and archives are not freely available for publication. Photographs can only be published with permission and in accordance with the established price list. Therefore, I will publish only publicly available data and data I have collected myself, including metadata.

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Material sources on traditional clothing in Riga during the 18th and 19th centuries

This dataset contains metadata, descriptions, and measurements of material sources on traditional clothing in Riga during the 18th and 19th centuries. The original sources are stored at the archives of museums. This dataset contains data on what information the analysed material sources can provide for dress historians and social history researchers.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Textual data
- Other

Data include measurements of historical garments.

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

50

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

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